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Welcome to our September 2022 newsletter

Bringing you news of past, present and future events and activities.

Along with our regular reports on schools, alumni and instructor profiles, and an update on Glosario - an open source multilingual lexicon of data science terminology - we will be showcasing some activities and work of the RDA and CODATA. The RDA focus in this newsletter edition is on Groups involved in Open and Responsible Research; read about 3 RDA Interest Groups working in this field, and decide if you would like to join them. CODATA have reached the final review stage for the CODATA RDM Terminology 2022; read on for full details and participate in the public feedback of the expert review - deadline 30th September.

Data Atlanta 2022

7 Sept - 3 November 2022

The [CODATA-RDA Schools of Research Data Science](#) (SoRDS) began its first US-based event with an introduction and welcoming session on 7 September, 2022. This hybrid version of the SoRDS event will be delivered virtually between now and 3 November with in-person sessions on 12 and 13 October. The event is hosted by the [South Big Data Hub](#) in collaboration with the [AIM-AHEAD Southeast Hub at Morehouse School of Medicine](#), and [Microsoft](#). The curriculum focuses on researcher Data Science Training through a mix of virtual and in-person instruction. This will be the first CODATA-RDA School run in the United States and will include teams from universities with the AIM-AHEAD Southeast Hub. The SMART-DART: Health Equity Cohort will focus on growing the competence of Health Equity researchers in accessing, analyzing, visualizing, and publishing data. 39 participants from minority serving institutions (MSIs) have been chosen to attend. This activity will cover topics on principles and practice of Open Science, research data

More details available [here](#)

Curriculum materials openly available [here](#)

South Africa | São Paulo School of Research Data Science

9 May - 15 July 2022 - Online and Self-Paced

Raphael Cóbe, Bianca Peterson, Martie VanDeventer

The 2nd virtual CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science, hosted by the University of Pretoria, South Africa and ICTP-SAIFR, Sao Paulo - Brazil was the first joint school that brought together events in 2 continents. The school hosted 101 participants from 14 countries (see map below) (5 of these in South/Central America; 8 African countries and Indonesia). The school provided early career researchers (undergraduate to postdoc) with foundational data science skills, which includes technical skills and responsible research practices, to enable them to work with their data in an effective and efficient manner as is required by 21st century research. The material covered by the programme is fundamental to all areas of research, and thus applicable to researchers and professionals from all disciplines that deal with significant amounts of research data.

This year the school happened entirely online and students followed the lectures and did the exercises in a self-paced way. The school lasted for 10 weeks and covered a different theme each week. Instructors and helpers continually monitored Slack for any questions and provided feedback in a timely manner. We also hosted two live Q&A sessions every week during which instructors addressed any additional questions participants may have had. The content was provided as video lectures as well as presentation slides and most of the sessions also involved practical exercises.

The Summer School was facilitated using the e-learning platform hosted by the University of Pretoria, South Africa. Several role-players collaborated to make the Data School a reality. South African representation came from the Data Intensive Research Initiative of South Africa (DIRISA), the South African Centre for Digital Language Resources (SADiLaR), the Network of Data and Information Curation Communities (NeDICC), Data Carpentry SA and the Department of Information Science, University of Pretoria. On the Sao Paulo side, the ICTP South American Institute for Fundamental Research (ICTP-SAIFR), the Institute of Theoretical Physics of the Sao Paulo State University (IFT-Unesp) and the Sao Paulo Research and Analysis Center (SPRACE) were represented. In total, 66 participants managed to complete the summer school and received a certificate of attendance.

Participants appreciated having support from Spanish and Portuguese speaking

channels, in any of the languages, and helpers assisted as required.

Some other useful comments we received from the post-School survey confirmed that a hybrid model was very useful to those who also need to keep laboratory experiments going or are employed in office jobs. They indicated that they were able to use their personal time to study the training material. We would therefore, in future, investigate the possibility of continuing with a hybrid model. We were also asked to investigate Python as an extension of R (and not as an alternative). This is something that will receive serious consideration. Similarly most respondents indicated that OpenRefine is an application that is of immediate use to them and that they will continue making use of it. We will therefore refrain from moving Open Refine into the preparatory phase of the Data School. All respondents indicated that Slack was a very useful and easy to use tool that provided useful additional support. Although participants did not all necessarily post questions they appear to have monitored the responses to the questions posted. We realise that we need to further investigate the delivery platform as all participants did not find the navigation easy to negotiate. Finally, we may need to reconsider the idea that we could post the learning content as a self paced, self-study unit. Respondents were unsure whether they would have mastered the content without guidance from the facilitators and helpers.

All-in all, the collaborative effort to facilitate two Schools simultaneously was considerably easier and more effective than what we had anticipated. It is a model that we could recommend to others. The reach is considerably bigger and the effort to host the School is reduced because more hands are available to share the responsibilities. We wish to thank all the participants who made this a pleasant, learning experience for us all.

The First Hybrid School

SoRDS had the first opportunity to return to partial in-person participation following 2 years of virtual schools from July 11-22. The school was held at the ICTP in Trieste and was in a hybrid format so there were students attending in person and other students who were attending online in a live fashion.

We welcomed 14 students at our regular host site, ICTP in Trieste, Italy and were joined by 47 virtual attendees. 24 countries were represented overall.

Virtual machines were used to ensure that everyone would have the required software without having to install it themselves. All the materials and information were shared in a central place and participants could easily access it at any time. However, some participants did experience some challenges, such as connection issues and different time zones, which caused them to fall behind with some of the lessons. Nevertheless, participants provided positive feedback and agreed that the hybrid school was a success - see the helper and alumni profiles below.

CODATA Activities

Ending on good terms: the CODATA RDM Terminology 2022 reaches final review stage

Laura Molloy, Senior Research Lead, CODATA

Terminologies are useful tools to support interoperability and efficiency in research data management and in discussions about this practice. In such a collaborative field, if we don't agree on a shared meaning of a specific term then we're in danger of misunderstanding each other and missing potential points of connection. With that in mind, I'm pleased to work with an international set of colleagues interested in the key terms of Research Data Management (RDM) to review and improve the resource formally known as the CASRAI RDM Glossary.

The CASRAI Glossary was intended as a practical reference for individuals and groups concerned with the improvement of research data management. In 2020, CASRAI asked CODATA to assume responsibility for the curation of this valued resource. This is a natural fit given our previous participation in the stewardship and development of this resource, and our links with a heterogenous range of task groups, working groups and national committees, as well as important initiatives such as the Schools of Research Data Science. giving us a rich network of expertise on which to draw.

We realised that the real power of the resource was its ability to support meaning across different contexts, making it a terminology, rather than a glossary. Next, I was keen to

pragmatic annual process between late 2021 and summer 2022 to review the set of terms and suggest edits, additions and removals that were required. The terminology is not an attempt to list every concept, tool and standard relevant to RDM; rather, it focuses on terms without easily found authoritative definitions elsewhere and offers an accessible definition in the context of contemporary RDM.

Working together

Seventeen WG members from Africa, Asia, Europe and the Americas collaborated via calls and asynchronous methods to choose the terms they would review and – for each term that they reviewed – whether they wished to:

- accept the term and its definition in its current form;
- edit it (and specify the proposed edits);
- or remove it.

In the end, we removed around a third of the terms of the previous set. Terms were removed if they were considered by the expert WG to be beyond the published [scope](#) of the RDM Terminology. Many of the removed terms appear to have been from related but distinct domains (particularly research practice, project management and computing science). Removal is no reflection on the quality of the definition writing of previous contributors, but mostly due to scope issues. We are left with 345 terms in the current (2022) edition, so whilst we have definitely trimmed the size of the resource and sharpened its focus, it is still a rich and extensive terminology.

We aim to keep the CODATA RDM Terminology relevant by maintaining it as a 'living document'. A lightweight review will be performed by a freshly-recruited expert working group each year, in order to keep the terminology fresh, up to date and useful to those working in research, data management, digital curation and preservation, research management, research policy, open data advocacy, computer science, information management, research administration, library, scholarly publishing, digital archiving and research funding roles.

Get involved

- The results of the 2021-22 expert review are now out for public feedback: [please review and comment by 30 Sept 2022!](#)
- Interested in applying to be a member of the next RDMT WG? Make sure you [join the CODATA International News list](#) to be alerted when we open membership for the 2023 review cycle.
- Visit [the WG page](#) for the latest news on the RDMT.
- For any queries about the RDMT, please contact WG convenor at [laura\[at\]codata.org](mailto:laura[at]codata.org)

Open and Responsible Research

Data for Development Interest Group

How can the RDA Data for Development IG support Open and Responsible Research in East Africa to reduce the research capacity gap and infrastructural challenge?

Universities are the largest research entities in developing countries, yet their investment in open access platforms and institutional repositories is dismal. One of the reason for forming the

Data for Development RDA Interest Group (IG) was to eliminate data illiteracy and data poverty. Universities are one of the pivotal points to eradicate data poverty through skilling and re-orientation of how research and innovation are done. The biggest challenge for most of the universities in East Africa is the limited budget for research and low investment in research infrastructure. This means many researchers lack the skills and supportive infrastructure to deliver open and responsible research.

Open and responsible research needs to be supported by skilled researchers as well as offering a supportive infrastructure for open, transparent research processes.

The mapping of research publications and journals shows that most of the research in developing countries is published in international journals run in developed countries. Firstly, the local research publishing platforms are not widely accessible, and the standards of locally published materials needs to be enhanced. Secondly, the absence of a substantial number of local open-source archiving of research and datasets is limiting the ability of early career researchers to engage in open and responsible research.

The above challenges reaffirm the need for inter-university and industry collaborations, networking, and early career researchers' development to advance responsible research that impacts the Africa continent. The Data for Development IG is involved in several initiatives to promote skills of early career researchers and support open and responsible research. These initiatives are empowered by the existing collaboration between institutions of the Data for Development members. These organizations include:

- Dlab – with a large data lab. In East Africa is just a kind of facility to support open and responsible research [\[link\]](#)
- EASRN – with members of 14 institutions in East Africa is a coordination effort for inter-university infrastructural development [\[link\]](#)
- NEMRA – with a membership of more than 300 researchers is collaborating to build capacity of early career researchers [\[link\]](#)
- GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences – an international partner with renown experience in supporting open data science and repository management [\[link\]](#)

a strategy, the Data for Development IG and its partners (GESIS – Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences and East Africa Scientific Research Network) will use the forthcoming International Summer School in Uganda ([link](#)) to develop a blended learning and fair data training materials. An evaluation of the blended materials will be done in November.

[International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group](#)

The call for Indigenous data sovereignty (IDSov) —the right of a nation to govern the collection, ownership, and application of its own data—has grown in intensity and scope since 2015. Following the publication of the freely downloadable [Indigenous Data Sovereignty: Toward an Agenda](#) (2016) a global network of IDSov national-level networks formed the RDA [International Indigenous Data Sovereignty Interest Group](#) in 2017. The goals of the Interest Group are clearly aligned with the RDA mission of creating a global community to develop and adopt infrastructure that promotes data-sharing, data-driven research, and data use. Interest Group members are strong advocates for data-driven research and data use, and are also working in varied ways to build data capabilities beyond academic institutions, so as to benefit Indigenous communities. The Interest Group has hosted numerous RDA Plenary sessions, including a workshop at the RDA/International Data Week in Gaborone, Botswana in 2018 which led to the creation of the [CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance](#) (2019), released by the Global Indigenous Data Alliance (GIDA) and published in [CODATA's Data Science Journal](#) (2020). Interest Group members also contributed to chapters from the 2nd co-edited book, [Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Policy](#) (2020, free download) and collaborated with the RDA [FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group](#) to publish on [Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR Principles for Indigenous data futures](#) (2021). The CARE principles appear in the [UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science](#), the [AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research](#), the [Aotearoa New Zealand Antarctic and Southern Ocean Research Directions and Priorities](#), and the [RDA COVID-19 Indigenous Data Guidelines](#). Current Interest Group efforts, in collaboration with GIDA, national networks, Indigenous Peoples, and individuals, are developing implementation strategies for the CARE Principles and supporting Indigenous-led data strategies, from community data governance to repositories. This includes work with IEEE to develop a [Recommended Practice for the Provenance of Indigenous Peoples' Data](#), LICCI for [Research on Indigenous Data Governance Protocols](#), and [Local Contexts](#) to apply Traditional Knowledge (TK) and Biocultural (BC) Labels. We seek to attract new members, including researchers, repository stewards, data users, and Indigenous communities.

[Sharing Rewards and Credit \(SHARC\) Interest Group](#)

(IG) is a volunteer member-based working group established along with various scientific communities and fields within the RDA community. The Group's efforts are focused on unpacking and improving rewarding mechanisms in the research data/resources sharing process by providing a set of recommendations towards relevant stakeholders. The goal is to drive the implementation and adoption of Open Science- and FAIR-based rewarding research pathways and performance indicators for these activities, such as data sharing, in the research evaluation processes at the institutional, national and European/international levels. SHARC IG has joined the global multi-stakeholder coalition on reforming research assessment coordinated by the European Commission that has recently issued an Agreement available [here](#).

The main activities of the group can be followed through the [Zenodo RDA-SHARC IG community](#).

Notably, the group's activities have so far led to the development of a tool that helps assess to what extent one's dataset complies with the FAIR principles. This template has been described and published in David et al. 2020. The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles. Data Science Journal, 19(1), p.32. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-032>.

As the notions of Open and Responsible Research include ethics principles and how to include them operationally in data research, SHARC IG included a conference and discussion in one of its RDA P15 plenary sessions in April 2020: "[Ethics and ethical values in FAIR literacy training](#)". Developed in collaboration with the EU co-funded project [FAIRplus](#), two elements have since been produced: 1) an [online module for young scholars](#) that includes resources on data ethics and 2) an analysis of values associated with FAIR principles ([Ethical values of FAIR](#)). Such values are essential not only in training but also in the evaluation process of research, and Open Science activities, as addressed in SHARC-IG.

In April 2022, RDA-SHARC IG [launched a global online survey](#) to understand the perceptions and expectations of various research communities regarding how Open Science activities, such as research data sharing, are (or should be) taken into consideration and rewarded. The results will help guide future recommendations towards various stakeholder groups involved in research evaluation. [Preliminary results of this survey were presented](#) at the 19th RDA Plenary SHARC IG session on the 20th of June 2022 during the International Data Week 2022. The survey is still open until October 1, 2022 and it is available in three languages through the following links: [English](#), [Spanish](#), [Korean](#).

We invite everybody to participate in this survey, regardless of your job position (researcher, professor, PhD student, research funder, librarian, data specialist, etc.). Upon completion of the survey and analysis of the responses, the main outcomes will be uploaded to the Zenodo RDA-SHARC IG community.

Instructor Profile

Hugh Shanahan

Hi, my name is Hugh and I am one of the co-chairs of the schools.

I've been involved with the schools since their inception. It's been great to watch the schools evolve and grow. Back in the early 2010's I worked very closely with Andrew (Harry) Harrison. We noticed that students from Low and Middle Income Countries (LMICs) would make great progress during a PhD in a High Income Country (HIC) and then encounter great difficulties returning to their home institution. From our interactions at the Research Data Alliance plenary meetings it became clear that the major problem was the training gap for ECRs and hence these schools came into being. Both the RDA and CODATA realised the importance of running the schools at that point. Soon afterwards the ICTP came on board and they have been essential partners ever since.

I have a fairly meandering research background. I started out working in High Energy (Particle) Physics working in the 90's. This was very computational work rather than scribbling on a white board and started that point when thinking about dealing with data is as important as the software. I switched to Bioinformatics, working at University College London and then the European Bioinformatics Institute near Cambridge in the UK where I looked at Protein-DNA interactions. In 2005 I started as a lecturer at the Computer Science department and spent about ten years working on transcriptomic data. It was around this point I started working on the schools and have more or less entirely pivoted to thinking about Open Science since then.

There is a running joke that the only reason I got involved with the schools was it gave me a chance to learn everything that I needed to know about analysing data. That's not true! But I've loved the chance to get a deeper understanding of a variety of different topics such as RDM and the ethics behind Open and Responsible Research.

Helper Profile

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My Name is Leani Bothma and I attended the CODATA-RDA summer school in Trieste in July 2017 for my future PhD studies in Environmental Microbiology at the North-West University (NWU), South Africa. On my return, I volunteered as an instructor/helper for the Metagenomics Data Carpentry Workshop in October 2017 at the NWU. I also volunteered as an online helper for the 2021 African CODATA-RDA summer school and in 2022 I was happy to virtually return to Trieste as an online helper for CODATA-RDA summer school in Trieste.

Initially, I needed to learn the skills taught in the Software and Data Carpentry workshops for analysing the genomic data of viruses and bacteria after exposure to emerging contaminants in environmental water. But the skills taught during the summer school have proven to be valuable to my career even outside of the environmental science and genomics fields. I was working as an administrative assistant for the Faculty of Engineering at the NWU and when they wanted to create their own student database for their Higher Degrees students I could raise my hand with confidence as I had coding and data analysis experience thanks to the CODATA-RDA summer school in Trieste in 2017 for my PhD studies. Now I work as a Systems and Process Developer and Data Scientist for the Engineering Faculty, maintaining and upgrading the previously mentioned database. In addition, I spend two-month periods working with one of their faculty's administrative processes and then finding innovative ways to automate the repetitive tasks the administrators have to do. After implementing and training the administrative assistant on the new system or process I move on to the next process. A far cry from my environmental science education but very satisfying and all because of the skills first learned and continue to learn by staying part of the Carpentry community.

Alumni Profile

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Motahareh Torki

You may have seen the gorgeous images of the James Webb Space Telescope. A lot more data is observed from the sky every night to provide us with information about the mysterious universe. In the era of giant telescopes and modern instruments, astronomy became a resource for producing big data. Hence, the role of data science is undeniable these days and data-driven astronomy is evolving into a rapidly growing field of study.

My name is Motahare Torki from Iran. I am a predoctoral researcher with an M.Sc. degree in Astrophysics and Cosmology and I was an online helper at the Data Schools Summer School, Trieste in July 2022. My interests lie at the intersection of computational astrophysics and data science, where you can investigate data from the sky.

I first got to know data science during my Master's. My Master's thesis was about applying a deep learning approach to detect the imprints of Cosmic Strings in CMB data observed by the Planck satellite. CMB is the leftover radiation from the Big Bang that fills the entire universe, allowing astronomers to study the evolution of the universe since its earliest time. Cosmic strings are hypothetical structures that may be formed in the early universe, and we wanted to find evidence for their existence in CMB observations. For that, I trained a CNN using simulations, and this model's predictions on Planck CMB observations were what we were looking for.

My other works also include the classification of astronomical objects based on photometric data. Currently, I am using deep learning to detect clouds and rainfall forecasts at the Iranian National Observatory site using all-sky images. It is now my intention to pursue a Ph.D. in astronomical data science.

At the Summer School, it was admirable how the instructors and organizers tried to keep every participant, whether online or in-person, on the same page. The most important aspect of this school is its comprehensiveness. Everybody, regardless of their background and prior experience, will benefit from it since it covers a wide range of topics related to research data science. The school brought me the opportunity to learn R, which will be extremely helpful for my research. The summer school also introduced me to many methods and tools for doing open and responsible research. The biggest advantage of this school for me was that I got to know people with the same interests as mine. It would be

Alumni Profile

Andrews Frimpong Adu

I am a Ph.D. candidate in Biodata Analytics and Computational Genomics at Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Ghana, at the time of writing. My study focuses on methods for expressing genome graphs that require less computational power and less memory storage. Given the huge genetic diversity and variability of African people and the massive genomic data sets presently accessible, developing tools that can successfully act on genomic data sets is critical for understanding variability in African populations. My research interests include bioinformatics, Data science, and machine intelligence.

My research entails analyzing vast amounts of biological data and making sense of it. Although I had previously worked with programming and machine learning tools, the 2022 CODATA-RDA Research Data Science School in Trieste, Italy, allowed me to delve deeper and learn new data science tools and approaches. It also enabled me to consolidate and strengthen my past knowledge and expertise with the tools and applications I often utilized. The program was a brilliant experience. I learned many coding skills through practical hands-on sessions on techniques and applications for handling large-scale data on various computing infrastructures, including high-performance computing platforms. This experience has enhanced my knowledge and skills in Biodata analytics. I also became acquainted with the notions of "Open and Responsible Conduct of Research and Research data management to Authorship in the 21st century," which are essential for all researchers. Most significantly, I learned how a group of dedicated and compassionate researchers could come together to provide such an incredible learning experience for individuals worldwide. And I feel this has set a solid foundation for future collaborations.

practice at my institution.

Glosario

Andiswa Bukula, South African Centre for Digital Language Resources

What is Glosario?

The Carpentries first announced Glosario in July of 2020 as an open source, multilingual lexicon of terminology used in data science. Nearly 200 additional terms in English and numerous other definitions in other languages have been added to the glossary since that blog article was published. The resource's prospective benefits include assisting lesson creators and maintainers in making their contents easier to find, enabling students to see connections between classes, and assisting students who do not speak English well in understanding the subject.

This online term dictionary and library is accessible in R and Python. By including glossary keys in the lesson's metadata, authors can specify what the lesson covers, what students should know before they begin, and where they can go to acquire that information. Additionally, authors can use the library's features to add standardized hyperlinks to terminology and meanings in any of the many (human) languages they employ in their classes.

Due to the nature of such a resource and its importance, Glosario was then introduced again at the CODATA-RDA School of Research Data Science Summer School which ran virtually 3 May – 9 July 2021. The purpose of introducing Glosario to the CODATA Summer Schools was to provide Early Career Researchers an opportunity to be part of such a project so that their languages could be represented. Currently the following languages are represented on Glosario:

[Afrikaans](#)

[Deutsch](#)

[Bangla](#)

[Ελληνικά](#)

[English](#)

[Español](#)

[Français](#)

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and we would like to see more contributions from the African continent because a resource like this is pertinent to the development of our African languages because such resources are limited when it comes to under resourced African languages.

How to contribute to Glosario.

Anyone possessing a basic familiarity with the GitHub web interface can get involved! For individuals who are unsure about using GitHub, this is a fantastic chance to become familiar with the platform while also putting their knowledge to use in the future to the advantage of others. Then, individuals who have more GitHub experience are urged to participate because the value of the resources for everyone increases as more terminology and translations become available in Glosario.

During the Summer School, the participants were encouraged to contribute towards the glossary in their mother tongue by translating a few scientific terms.

There is a [detailed and accessible guide for contributing](#), which has been translated into several languages. Contributions are welcome in any language, not only those represented in that document. If you need help with your contribution, feel free to come ask questions on the [#glosario](#) Slack channel (if you are not a member of The Carpentries Slack you can join by filling [this form](#)).

Alternatively one can visit the following links for further information

- <https://carpentries.org/blog/2020/10/hacktoberfest-2020-glosario/>
- <https://carpentries.github.io/glosario/>
- <https://github.com/carpentries/glosario>
- <https://the-turing-way.netlify.app/collaboration/github-novice.html>

Or contact Angelique van Rensburg, one of the project organisers, for more details:

angelique [at] carpentries.org

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